

What Kind of Problems are Seen Common in the Adolescent Health Clinic during Pandemic Period?

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Abstract: *Adolescence is a developmentally unique period and the psychosocial consequences of the “age-determined” curfew should not be overlooked. Individualization and changes in intellectual development are the most important developmental tasks during adolescence. An age-stratified curfew may be perceived as a suppression of their own will, plans, and decisions. A distinct method of curfew involving adolescents and young adults were taken.*

The difference is on behaviors between youth and teenage during COVID-19 pandemic that Youth are intellectually better equipped than younger children to understand what is going on, authorities should explain to this unique group more clearly the importance of abiding. By following the curfew; they are aiding in problem-solving, saving lives, being the unseen heroes for the elderly people.

The aim is the study that why anxiety and depression are seen more than the normal period during pandemic period. And how we are able to overcome this struggle among youth without taking any longterm troubles.

Keywords: *Covid-19 pandemic, Youth, Adolescent Health clinic.*

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Turkey has a relatively young population compared with other European countries. There are 25.5 million children and adolescents younger than 20 years, and when combined with the 7.5 million people older than 65 years, The ratio of the population on lockdown accounts for 40% of the total population (83.15 million in accordance with the Turkish Statistical Institute).

Adolescents, a vulnerable population, have been carrying on their school curriculums online and conducting daily activities indoors since the outbreak of COVID-19 in China. This life-style transformation and threat of being infected may cause depressive and anxious disorders (Chen et al., 2020).

In young children and adolescents the pandemic and lockdown appeared to have a greater impact on emotional and social development compared to that in the grown-ups Government restrictions such as closures of schools, play grounds, and recreation centres (Sandu et al., 2019), lead to physical separation from peers, isolation, and less time spent outdoors, local increase in child/adolescent rates of depression and anxiety (Magson et al., 2021).

A feeling of responsibility in the active participation of problem-solving; Encourage adolescents to more logically consider the consequences of this pandemic, allowing them to hypothetically evaluate the pros and cons of this curfew. Adjusting boundaries for teens within the home may help create a balance between freedom and responsibility. During the curfew, "Confidentiality" stands for more independence and more emotional distance that adolescents want between them and the household. Developmentally, the adolescent's focus shifts from the family to peers and they need to build independent social relationships and acquire social roles within peer groups. Social isolation or Distancing, We should be using the terminology as "physical distancing." Separation from peers is a lot more stressful during adolescence, so explaining to them that this separation is only physical is critical. Globally, adolescents are devoted users of online technology which can be used during this time to keep them connected to peers, so they should be encouraged by family members to be creative in finding new ways to interact with friends (Luca et al., 2020).

Supporting Young Adults to rise to the challenge of COVID-19 (Lee, 2020), Respect young adults and leverage their strenghts rather than chastise them. We should support them to adhere to new public health guidance to prevent the spread of COVID-19.

They have some duties for their communities. Responsibility for elderly people and other family members. All the young people understand

how concerning this disease is for them all. Listen and follow the recommendations in their communities.

We have much more seen some problems in the Adolescent Medicine Clinic during COVID-19 pandemic. Eating disorders problems, Anormal uterine bleeding, Depression, Anxiety, Attemp to the suicide, Cancelled young people's sport activities, art performance and graduations (Grigoras & Ciubara, 2021). We pointed out that anxiety is %25, depression is %30 more than the normal period during COVID-19 pandemic.

The important points for adolescence are these in order into the World. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) The legal age of adulthood in the World is 18, brain and cognitive development continues from adolescence through the late 20s. Young adults are still developing the ability to set long-term goals and delay gratification. While teenagers get a bad rap, young adults actually engage in more risk behaviors than teenagers. Young adults have higher rates of substance use (Hawke, 2020) and sexually transmitted infections than teenagers. Missing a much anticipated spring break trip with friends may seen worse than catching a virus.

Law and regulations due to COVID-19 challenge young adults' independence and autonomy. Young adulthood is traditionally marked by less time spent with parents and more time spent with peers and romantic partners. Owing to social distancing, young adults may be separated from their peers and romantic partners. College students have returned home unexpectedly, after a period of living independently in dooms, and thus feel that they have regressed (Magson et al., 2021).

The principles to foster healthful behavior changes in adolescents and young adults are these for COVID-19 (Nagata, 2020).

Respect; Any communication or advice to young people should address their desire for status and respect rather than threatening them. Acknowledge that social distancing rules may be challenging for everyone. Young adults may also respond to stories or posts who share creative alternatives to cope with social distancing.

Motivation; Motivational interview is commonly used with young adults, particularly in dealing with addiction or mental illness (Racine et al., 2020). This technique engages with the young person to explore their own motivations for change. The young people is allowed to analyze the potential risks and benefits that are associated with their behaviors, thus supporting them to make their own informed choices.

Privacy; Give young adults some privacy while home. Allowing a young person some private time at home to talk with friends or romantic partners may prevent them from having to physically leave the home to get

private time. Parents might allow their young adults more leeway to keep in touch with their friends and peers virtually so they do not have to meet in person.

Strengths; Young adults have many strengths, and leveraging these may be a win-win for all involved. Young people are experts at distant socializing through social media and virtual communications. They can help families to keep connected virtually and troubleshoot technical issues as families work from home.

Conclusion

The first COVID-19 case in Turkey was officially confirmed on the 11th March 2020, the same day the WHO declared the disease a pandemic. As of March 16th, schools and universities in Turkey were closed. To our knowledge, Turkey is the only country worldwide to apply a unique age-stratified curfew; this first started for seniors older than 65 years (as of 21st March 2020) and followed by the curfew order for children and youth younger than 20 years (starting 5th April 2020).

The best solutions on adolescents are these in order during COVID-19 pandemic. Families should be encouraged to create spaces that will allow their teens; the freedom to be themselves at home, stay connected with friends, while at the same time both gaining emotional adaptations, resilience to unpredictable life events, saving lives by staying at home.

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